

practiced, and harvest was in late Dec.

Water depth was recorded weekly. SB were caught daily from 1800 to 2200 h in a light trap 200 m from the field. Each morning the catch was recorded. The first SB were trapped the 2d wk of Jul (see figure). Population increased rapidly between late Sep and late Oct, then declined. Every 2 wk, 10 plants were randomly collected and height, stem length, and number of internodes of the main shoot were recorded. At harvest, 140 plant samples were collected, and percent SB damage at different internodes of the main stem was recorded (see figure).

Almost no SB were trapped at early seedling growth when soil was dry. During early elongation (Jul-Sep), when almost all of the stems were submerged, SB infested few plants. Peak SB infestation was at preflowering. At harvest, damage was low in the 13th internode, but was substantially higher in the last 3 internodes (see figure).

Data on peak SB emergence reflect the period of maximum plant infestation. Also, SB infestation increases with decreasing water level. *ℳ*

Percent SB-damaged internodes (base to apex) of deep water rice plants at harvest and variations of light trap catch, water level, plant height, stem length, and number of internodes, West Bengal, India.

Stem borer infestation on hybrid rice

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Hybrid rice was released in China in 1978. Since then, striped stem borer (SSB) *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker) and yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* damage has increased. SSB attacks rice in Hunan, Jiangxi, Jiangsu, Zhejiang, and Sichuan Provinces, and YSB damages rice in southern Jiangxi and Fujian, and northern Guangdong.

In surveys at the HAAS farm beginning in 1978, we found that SSB populations in hybrid rice fields were 28 to 36% higher than in other rice fields and that there were 107 to 170% more egg masses. There are 7 to 17 times as many YSB egg mass as in other rice fields.

Survival rates of SSB larvae during 3 yr were 8, 18, and 19% higher on hybrid than on other rices, and YSB larvae survival was 13 to 20% higher. Larvae and pupae of SSB that fed on hybrid rice weighed 17 and 13% more than those collected from other rices. The mean weights over 2 yr of SSB pupae that fed on hybrid rice were 30 and 32% higher than the weights of those that fed on other rices. The first year, SSB females grown on hybrid rice produced 46 to 103 eggs/female; in the second and third years, they produced 46 to 82 more eggs/female than SSB females reared on other rices.

YSB larvae reared on hybrid rice weighed an average 63 mg. Those reared on other rices weighed an average 51 mg. YSB females produced an average 262 eggs/female on hybrid rice and 224 eggs/female on other rices. Over 4 yr, YSB hibernating on hybrid rice had 89,

23, 40, and 46% mortality vs 11, 9, 21, and 24% on other rices.

Most hybrid rice lines have large stems, heavy foliage, thick sheath, and long duration, which may favor SSB and YSB development. *ℳ*

The correct name of the African rice stem-boring Diopsidae (stalk-eyed fly)

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In the 1950s a stalk-eyed fly (Diopsidae) was identified as an important rice stem borer in Africa. The fly became known as *Diopsis thoracica* Westwood, 1837. Subsequently most authors wrote that *thoracica* was a junior synonym of *Diopsis macrophthalma* Dalman, 1817, which had *Diopsis longicornis*